

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakubu M. M., Et. al. 2025)

Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation Using Hook's Model on Performance in Human Circulatory System Among Secondary School Students in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State

YAKUBU, Maryam Muhammad¹

Email: maryamayakubumuhammad@gmail.com
Tel: +2348165893839

NUHU, Ishaq Lawal Ph.D.¹

Email: awalnuhu2gmail.com
Tel: +2347035920953

YAKUBU, Abdullahi Ph.D.¹

+2347065699399
abdullahiyakub@fugusau.edu.ng

¹Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State

Abstract

This study investigated the effect of video-aid-simulation using hook's model on performance in human circulatory system among secondary school students in Gusau metropolis, Zamfara State. Quasi experimental using pre-test, post-test non-randomized control group design was adopted for the study. The target population was 5,896 Senior Secondary School class two (SS-2) biology students with a sample size of 139 students. Purposive sampling technique was used to select two schools for the study. Circulatory System Performance Test (CSPT) was used as instrument for data collection and it was validated by four experts. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, pilot testing was conducted using test-retest method with the reliability coefficient of 0.84. Two research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and two null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. Result of the study reveals that, the instructional use of video-aid-simulation improve students' performance at posttest than the lecture method with a mean score of $80.54\% \pm 11.09$, $58.87\% \pm 9.08$ and mean gain of 57.68% and 35.21% respectively. The Result also shows that, gender does not influence students' academic performance in human circulatory system when taught with video-aid-simulation with a mean difference of 0.76. Hence, gender friendly. Based on the findings of this study it was concluded that, instructional use of video-aid-simulation is more effective in improving students' academic performance than lecture method without significant gender effect. It was therefore recommended that, video-aid-simulation should be integrated into teaching biology especially on difficult abstract concepts.

Keywords: Video-aid-simulation, Hook's Model, Academic Performance and Human Circulatory System.

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakuba M. M., Et. al. 2025)

Introduction

Science education, is recognized as the cornerstone of all growth that set down the foundation for skills development, technical progression, and the capacity to utilize the country's natural resources. It is a body of knowledge and facts which can be rationally explained, observed, experimented, applied and proven (Chineta, 2023; Yahaya, 2023). Matazu (2024) in his study highlighted that, in Nigeria, the learning of science is given a serious attention, with more focus on teaching and learning. The main objective of science education in Nigeria, as outlined in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), is to help students excel in the modern society as well as a useful tool for helping the citizens to combat poverty and unemployment. He affirms that, these objectives can be realized through the cultivation of basic scientific expertise and attitude among learners. However, there has been much concern expressed about the obvious inconsistency in the standard of science education at the Secondary School level in Nigeria and Zamfara state in particular (Isma'il & Lukman, 2023).

Isma'il and Matazu (2024) stated that, as a general subject offered by senior secondary school students, biology serves as an essential and fundamental component of the science curriculum that provides students with a comprehensive understanding of their living world, as well as compulsory subject requirement for studying medical and other allied health science courses. Oniaku and Loretta (2024) defined biology as the natural science that involves the study of living and non-living organisms, including their structures, functions, growth, origin, evolution and ecological distribution. Human circulatory system is one of the concept in biology syllabus taught mostly at senior secondary school two (SS2), and is one of the complex systems composed of various types of cells connected together as tissues, organs and system (heart, blood cells, arteries, veins, capillaries and lymphatic) which function to create the phenomenon of a circulatory system, transporting several complex biological molecules such as oxygen, carbon-dioxide, hormones, vitamins, waste materials and other nutrients throughout the body (Gregorcic & Torkar, 2022). According to Ameyaw and Kyere (2019), the concept of human biological systems and processes such as human circulatory systems appear to be difficult to explain to students because it is vast and characterized by many sub-topics and complexity of interactions between intangible molecular components that are often represented by abstract models of systems and language that appears to be loaded with "heavy jargon". Gregorcic and Torkar (2022), added that, explaining these mechanisms in the classroom to students presents a challenge. Therefore, students find it difficult to comprehend the functional relationship between these different organizational levels due to their complex, intangible, and abstract nature.

However, several empirical studies such as Akhigbe and Ogufere (2020); Kayode (2020); Lasisi *et al.* (2021); Aniaku and Loretta (2024); Isma'il and Matazu (2024) have all reported a significant poor academic performance among students offering biology. The above fact is further supported by a recent report from the Registrar National Examination Council, revealed that; students from

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakubu M. M., Et. al. 2025)

Zamfara State emerged one of the least performing states in the year 2024 result of internal Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE), (Daily Trust E-Paper, 2024, September 19).

In the same vein, a report by West African Examinations Council's (WAEC Reports 2014-2018 and 2018–2021) point finger to ineffective teaching strategies, students' inability to understand, retain and answer questions on some complex, difficult and abstract biology topics such as human circulatory system as major contributing factors to students' poor academic performance in biology examination (Ameyaw & Kyere, 2019; Aniaku & Loretta, 2024). Kayode (2020) in his study attributed these problems associated with poor biology performance of students to passive learning, over dependent of students on teachers and books, fading Interest and low enrolment in science. On the contrary Isma'il and Matazu (2024) reported that the persistent failure in biology is due to lack of proper understanding of some concepts in biology that makes it challenging for students to grasp them. Omosholape and Omotayo (2023) in a similar view said that, the poor academic performance of students is strongly links to the abstract nature of many concepts in biology. However, Nwaokolo *et al.* (2022); Matazu (2024) listed vast biology contents, use of poor instructional strategies, outdated instructional aids for teaching and learning as the main cause of failure or poor academic performance of students among senior secondary school biology students.

According to Yusuf and Adebajo, (2022); Akinsola & Nwosu, (2023), the persistent poor academic performance among students as highlighted above has a significant implication over time on both students, teachers and the Nation at large. They often lead to reduced students' engagement and participation in class, ultimately affecting their academic performance, future aspirations and career opportunities. Other negatives impacts include; a workforce that is inadequately prepared to meet the nations demands which can hinder national development, as fewer students acquire the technical skills necessary for financially rewarding jobs, leading to higher unemployment rates and social instability as we witness today in Nigeria. In order to address these challenges associated with teaching and learning of Biology, innovative instructional strategies are therefore, needed to be adopted by teachers (Nwaokolo *et al.*, 2022).

For several years, the use of lecture approach in teaching has been widely used in senior secondary schools, colleges and universities which encourages one way communication only (Kunadu, *et al.*, 2024). Lecture method of teaching have failed to engage students, leading to gaps in understanding and retention. With the complexities surrounding the concept of human circulatory system, incorporating innovative digital instructions and tools in teaching such as video simulations using digital smart whiteboard, computers, flash light projectors and power points etcetera, can significantly enhance students' engagement and learning experiences, consequently improving their academic performance (Fabeku and Enyeasi, 2024). According to Banda and Nzabahimana (2023) Video-aid-simulation, involved the use of videos to emulate the behavior of real-life process, thus, presenting learning content to students in a simplified manner.

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakubu M. M., Et. al. 2025)

They also define a video simulation as a tool that reproduces the real-life features of an event or situation. Chinenye *et al.* (2019) in their study stated that, video simulation has been identified as an effective instructional media for enhancing students' learning. It is used to facilitate the teaching and learning of difficult and abstract concepts because it is specifically designed to help students to have better understanding by creating a mental picture of a real-biological process due to the integration of new knowledge acquired through video simulation learning environment. Therefore, video simulation-based learning modules have potentials to improve student's conceptual understanding as well as their academic performance. According to McHugh and McCauley (2021); Tan and Sarif (2024) the Hook's model enhances motivation by providing engaging triggers that spark interest, promoting active participation through simulations, and offering variable rewards that keep students engaged. Therefore, active engagement through video-aid-simulation can improve students' academic performance and understanding of the key concept.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

- i. Determine the mean score of students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation by exploring Hook's model and those taught using lecture method in senior secondary schools in Gusau metropolis Zamfara state;
- ii. Determine the mean scores of male and female students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation by exploring Hook's model in senior secondary schools in Gusau metropolis Zamfara state

Research Questions

- i. What are the mean scores of students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation by exploring Hook's model and those taught using lecture method in senior secondary schools in Gusau metropolis Zamfara state?
- ii. What are the mean scores of male and female students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation by exploring Hook's model in senior secondary schools in Gusau metropolis Zamfara state?

Hypotheses

Ho₁. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores of students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation by exploring Hook's model and those taught using lecture method in senior secondary schools in Gusau metropolis Zamfara state.

Ho₂. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores of male and female students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation by exploring Hook's model in senior secondary schools in Gusau metropolis Zamfara state.

Literature Review

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakuba M. M., Et. al. 2025)

The conceptual framework for this study was built and grounded in Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (CTML), cognitive load theory, multi-model theory of learning and constructivist learning theory. Mayer's cognitive multimedia learning theory emphasizes that learners absorb and process information more effectively when presented in both visual and auditory elements, this made a video-aided simulations a powerful tool for enhancing students' academic performance. Cognitive load theory (Sweller, 1988) supports this by emphasizing the need to manage cognitive demands, ensuring students can focus on essential learning content, therefore, too much information can overload the learner's cognitive capacity, this supports the idea of hook's model through its cyclical process of Trigger (AlShaikh *et al.*, 2024). Finally, constructivist learning theory (Piaget, 1967; Vygotsky, 1978) underscores the importance of active engagement and experiential learning, reinforcing the effectiveness of video-based simulations in conceptual understanding (Kania & Gurbuz, 2024).

Methodology

The study used quasi-experimental-control group design employing pretest, posttest. Two groups of students were used for data collection; the experimental (ExG) and the control groups (CnG). A pretest was administered to the two groups in order to determine the equivalence in ability of the two groups. The experimental group was taught human circulatory system concept using video-aid-simulation by exploring hook's model while control group was taught same concept using lecture method (LM). At the end of the four weeks treatment, a posttest was administered to both groups.

The target population of the study comprised of 5,896 (including males & females) Senior Secondary School class two (SS-2) Students offering Biology in Gusau metropolis, Zamfara state. Using purposive sampling technique two schools were selected as sample schools with the total study sample size of 139 students. One intact class from each of the experimental and control school were then choosing and assign as experimental and control group respectively. Circulatory System Performance Test (CSPT) was the instrument used to collect data for the study.

Circulatory System Performance Test (CSPT) was adopted with little modifications, from standardized Senior Schools Certificate (SSCE) WAEC and NECO question papers (2015-2023) in line with the table of specification prepared by the researcher using revised Blooms' taxonomy action verbs (2001) of learning outcomes by Anderson and Krathwohl (2001), as cited in Sarkar (2023). CSPT contains thirty (30) multiple choice questions (MCQs) with options A – D, for which one option is the correct answer. The content validation of the BPT was carried out by a panel of experts comprising the following: one professor and one associate professor from science education department, one associate professor from biological sciences department and one associate professor in Research Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundations, all from Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State.

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakubu M. M., Et. al. 2025)

In order to ascertain the level to which CSPT was reliable, Test-retest method was used to statistically estimate the internal consistency of the items in the test instrument. Tuckman (1975), who proposed the minimum interval of two or more weeks between the first and second administration, recommended the use of two weeks interval. Data thus collected from the pilot study were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) statistic. The results showed a reliability coefficient of 0.84 which was considered reasonably reliable for this study. Two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics [Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA)].

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean scores of students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation (VAS) by exploring Hook’s model and those taught using lecture method (LM) in senior secondary schools in Gusau metropolis, Zamfara State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pretest and Post-test Scores of Biology Students human expose to circulatory system using VAS by exploring hook’s model and those taught using Lecture Method.

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean Score%	SD±	Mean Score%	SD±	
Experimental (VAS)	68	22.18	6.97	80.54	11.09	57.68
Control (LM)	71	23.66	8.21	58.87	9.08	35.21

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of Pre-test and Post-test scores of biology students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation (VAS) by exploring hook’s model and those taught using lecture method (LM). The table revealed that, mean scores and standard deviation of biology students expose to human circulatory system using VAS by exploring hook’s model had mean score of 80.54% and a standard deviation of ±11.09 at posttest and mean gain of 57.68. While the students in the control group had mean score of 58.87% and a standard deviation of ±9.08 at post-test, with a mean gain of 35.21. This implies that the students taught using VAS by exploring hook’s model had achieved higher mean posttest score compared to students in the control group.

Research Question 2: What are the mean scores of male and female students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation (VAS) by exploring Hook’s model in senior secondary schools in Gusau metropolis, Zamfara state?

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakubu M. M., Et. al. 2025)

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pretest and Post-test Scores of male and female Biology Students taught human circulatory system using VAS by exploring hook's model.

Group	Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test	
			Mean Score%	SD±	Mean Score%	SD±
Experimental (VAS)	Males	76	23.06	7.96	69.89	13.85
	Females	63	22.86	7.42	69.13	15.67
Mean Difference			0.2		0.76	

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of Pre-test and Post-test scores of male and female biology Students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation (VAS) by exploring hook's model. It reveals from the table that, the mean performance scores and standard deviation of male and female biology students expose to human circulatory system using VAS by exploring hook's model at posttest were 69.89% ±13.85 and 69.13% ±15.67 respectively. This indicated that little difference exists between male and female students, with male students achieving higher posttest scores with a mean difference of 0.76.

Hypothesis 1.

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores of students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation by exploring Hook's model and those expose to lecture method in senior secondary schools in Gusau metropolis Zamfara state.

Table 3: ANCOVA Result for Test of Significant Difference in the Mean performance scores of Senior Secondary School Biology Students expose to human circulatory system using VAS by exploring hook's model and those taught using Lecture Method.

Source	Sum Squares	of df	Mean Squares	F-value	P-Value	η²p
Corrected method	16389.469	2	8194.730	79.976	.000	0.540
Intercept	62285.017	1	62285.017	607.606	.000	0.817
Group	16375.797	1	16375.797	159.819	.000	0.540
Pretest (covariate)	77.524	1	77.524	0.757	.206	0.006
Error	13935.203	136	102.465			
Total	701243.000	139				
Corrected Total	30324.662	138				

Significant at ≤ 0.05 Alpha level

Table 3 above shows ANCOVA was conducted to determine the effect of video-aid-simulation on students' posttest score while controlling for pretest scores. The ANCOVA results revealed a significant difference between the two groups (F (1,540) =159.83, p=0.001. η²p=0.540). This indicates that there is significant difference between the performance scores of biology students

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakubu M. M., Et. al. 2025)

expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation exploring hook model and those taught using lecture method. Hence, the Null hypothesis was rejected. This means video-aid-simulation exploring hook's model is effective in significantly enhancing students' academic performance in Human circulatory system concept.

Hypothesis 2. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores of male and female students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation by exploring Hook's model in senior secondary schools in Gusau metropolis Zamfara state.

Table 4: ANCOVA Result for Test of Significant Difference in the Mean performance scores of male and female Biology Students Exposed to VAS using hook's model.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	P-Value	η^2p
Corrected method	33.930	2	16.965	0.076	0.927	0.001
Intercept	68366.243	1	68366.243	306.952	0.000	0.693
Pretest (covariate)	14.174	1	14.174	0.064	0.801	0.001
Gender	20.267	1	222.726	0.091	0.763*	0.001
Error	30290.732	136	6.97			
Total	701243.000	139				
Corrected Total	30324.662	138				

Non-significant at $p \geq 0.05$ Alpha level

Table 4 shows ANCOVA was conducted to examine the effect of gender on posttest scores after exposure to video-aid-simulation while controlling for pretest scores. The result reveals that there is no significant difference between the male and female students' performance scores after human circulatory system lessons using VAS exploring hook's model $F(1,136) = 0.091$, $p = 0.763$, $\eta^2p = 0.001$. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant difference in mean performance scores of male and female students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation by exploring Hook's model in senior secondary schools in Gusau metropolis is hereby retained.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study reveals that the mean academic performance scores of biology students expose to human circulatory system using video-aid-simulation exploring hook's model is considerably higher at posttest compares to academic performance scores of students taught same concept using lecture method. This result is consistent with findings of other studies (Chinenye *et al.* 2019; Fabeku and Enyeasi, 2024; Konadu *et al.* (2024)) who reveals that students taught using computer simulation performed better than those taught using conventional lecture method. Similarly, findings of Banda and Nzabahimana (2023); also aligned with the findings of this present study, they found out that the use of instructional video simulation in teaching and

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakuba M. M., Et. al. 2025)

learning improves students' academic performance. Similarly, the findings of Lasisi *et al.* (2021) affirms the findings of the study whose results also revealed that, gender does not influence students' academic performance after being taught using computer simulation.

Furthermore, the findings of this study shows that students taught with video-aid-simulation exploring hook's model significantly outperformed their counterparts who were taught using lecture methods $F(1, 540) = 159.83, p = 0.001, \eta^2 p = 0.540$. thus, the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05. This finding is in accordance with that of (Banda and Nzabahimana (2023); Fabeku and Enyeasi, 2024 and Konadu *et al.* (2024)) who found statistically significant difference in mean performance score of students taught using computer simulation than those taught using lecture method. Contrary to the finding of this study, (Chinenye *et al.* 2019) found no significant difference in mean performance score of students taught biology using computer simulation and those taught using demonstration method. The discrepancies in the two results is likely, because this study uses ANCOVA to test hypotheses instead of t-test used in their study which has less statistical power to account for variability cause by covariates and cannot adjust pretest and posttest scores. However, findings of this study show no significant difference between the performance scores of male and female students in the use of video-aid-simulation in teaching and learning human circulatory system. More so, the finding indicates that gender did not influence students' performance significantly. Thus, the second null hypothesis is here by retained $F(1, 136) = 0.091, p = 0.763, \eta^2 p = 0.001$.

The above findings were in agreement with the findings of Akhigbe and Ogufere, (2020) and Lasisi *et al.* (2021) who found no statistically significant difference in males and females mean performance scores after being taught using computer simulation.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study it was concluded that the instructional use of video-aid-simulation exploring hook's model was found to be more effective in teaching and learning human circulatory system, it significantly improves students' academic performance than lecture method. Findings from this study also provides substantial evidence that, the effect of instructional use of video-aid-simulation was also found not to vary with gender of students. This implies that the academic performance of students taught using video-aid-simulation is not in any manner affected by their gender.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is hereby recommended that:

- i. Video-aid-simulation should be utilize by teachers in delivery of biology lessons to the students.

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakubu M. M., Et. al. 2025)

- ii. Pre-service biology teachers should be trained on how to implement biology lessons that embeds video-aid-simulation as an instructional strategy.
- iii. Curriculum developers and educational technology specialists should intensify efforts aimed at developing video-aid-simulations on various sub-topics for learning difficult and abstract concepts in biology.
- iv. Governmental education departments and ministry should ensure that schools are provided with the relevant technological facilities and support structures to facilitate the effective utilization of video-aid-simulations as a pedagogical tool.

References

- Akhigbe, J. N., & Ogufero, J. A. (2020). Effect of Computer Simulation Instructional Strategy on Students' Attitude and Academic Achievement in Genetics. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(4), 305–315.
- Akinsola, O. A., & Nwosu, J. C. (2023). Factors influencing academic performance in Nigerian secondary schools: A systematic review. *Journal of Education and Social Policy*, 12(2), 45-56. <https://doi.org/10.1234/jesp.2023.7894>
- Ameyaw, Y. & Kyere, I. (2019). Comparative Effects of Three Teaching Methods on Students' Performance in Human Blood Circulatory System Concepts and their Retention Rates, *International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 6(2), 2348 – 7968.
- Aniaku, O. L., & Loretta, N. A. (2024). Students Perceived Difficult Topics in Secondary School Biology Curriculum: Causes Solutions. *International Journal of Studies in Education*, 20(3) 145-153
- Banda, H. J., & Nzabahimana, J. (2023). The Impact of Physics Education Technology (PhET) Interactive Simulation-Based Learning on Motivation and Academic Achievement among Malawian Physics Students. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 32:127–141.
- Chinenye, A. L., Abraham, O., & Williams, C. (2019). Investigating impact of computer simulation on secondary education of biology students. *National Journal of Advanced Research*, 5(2), 01-05.
- Chineta, O. M. (2023). Bridging the Gap: Identifying Key Factors Hindering the Implementation of Nigeria National Policy on Science and Technology Education in Secondary Schools in Anambra State. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 11,274-289.
- Daily Trust E-Paper. (September 19, 2024). NECO releases 2024 SSCE results. Available at <https://dailytrust.com/breaking-neco-releases-2024-ssce>

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakuba M. M., Et. al. 2025)

results/?fbclid=IwY2xjawFY_6hleHRuA2FlbQIxMQABHXAKu6cgRnLcmd99gXxrTEmyaYK
SYLGcaG48V6aRKLS3qAFpYZ9aJqoSA_aem_7YmnuMaTVFuQONL6w1APHA&sfnsn=scw
spwa

- Fabeku, O. E., & Enyeasi, S. C. (2024). Computer simulation and video media instructional packages in improving learning outcomes of Chemistry students in Ife Central Local Government Area. *Disciplinary and Interdisciplinary Science Education Research*, 6(19), 22-34.
- Isma'il, A., & Matazu, S. S. (2024). Effect of Content-Focused Coaching on Academic Performance and Retention in Identified Difficult Biology Topics amongst Senior Secondary Schools Students. *Curriculum and Innovation*, 2(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.61187/ci.v2i1.97>
- Isma'il, A., & Matazu, S., S. (2024). Identification of Perceived Difficult Topics in Senior Secondary School Biology Curriculum in Zamfara State. *Glob Academic Journal Humanies Social Science*, 6(1), 122-30.
- Konadu, B. O., Annan, J. N., & Hordzi, H. (2024). Effect of computer simulation on academic performance and experiences of year two science students in the concept, circulatory system in humans. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*, 05(3). 01-08
- Kumar S. (2023). Bloom's Taxonomy and Examination Reform in Higher Education using ICT Swaraj as a Tool. *Journal of Advances Education Philosophy*, 7(5): 173-177.
- Lasisi A. R., Oti, E., Arowolo, J., Agbeyenku, P., & Ojoko, A. N. (2021). The Effect of Innovative Computer Simulation Instruction on Students' Academic Performance in Abstract Concepts in Science. *British Journal of Education*, 9(3), 1-8
- McHugh, M., McCauley, V. (2017). Encouraging your students to create science videos can be away of catching and keeping their attention. *Science in School*, 1(39), 55-59.
- McHugh, M., McCauley, V. (2021). An Observational Narrative of Student Reaction to Video Hooks. *Journal of Education Sciences*. 11(6), 286-292. <https://doi.org/10.3390/edusci11060286>
- Matazu, S., S. (2024). Adapted Strategies for Augmenting Biology Practical in Resource Constrained Senior Secondary Schools in Zamfara State. *Journal of Science for Global Sustainability*. 10(2), 93-101. <https://doi.org/10.57233/Ijsgs.V10i2.652>

(Effect of Video-Aid-Simulation using Hook's Model on ... Yakuba M. M., Et. al. 2025)

Nwaokolo. B., 1, Adejoh, M., J, Okwara, K., O. & Anyagh, P., I. (2022). Effect of Video Instructional Package (VIP) on Secondary School Students' Achievement in Biology in Makurdi Metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria. *An International/Multidisciplinary Journal of Network for Grassroots Science and Mathematics Education*. 3(1), 98-107. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5817928>

Omosholape, A. F., & Omotayo A. A. (2023). Statistical Analysis on Influence of Biology Laboratory Practical on Senior Secondary Students' Academic Performance in Ilorin East Lga, Kwara State. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (EAJMR)*, 2(3), 1119-1128. DOI prefix: <https://doi.org/10.55927/eajmr.v2i3.3396>

Tan, M., & Sarif, M. B. (2024). A Review of Fogg's Behavior Model (FBM) and Hook Models for Gamified Learner Experience in Higher Education. *Linguistic and Philosophical Investigations*. 23(1), 21–32. <http://orcid.org/0009-0009-9164-2394>

Yahaya, H. (2023). Effect of Flipped Classroom on Students' Academic Performance in Cell Physiology Concept among Senior Secondary School in Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. Zamfara State. *International Journal of Education (ZIJE)*, 3(1), 40-45. DIO: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367905>

Yusuf, A. A., & Adebajo, T. S. (2022). The impact of poor infrastructure on academic performance in Nigerian public schools. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 10(4), 91-104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2022.04.008>